

SHORT TERM MISSIONS

Short Term Missions (STMs) are small travel grants with the aim of:

- Sharing scientific expertise, methodologies, equipment and facilities to harmonise the existing approaches and methodologies within the large OHEJP European network
- Driving the research forward in a collaborative and non-duplicative fashion to strengthen both the scientific capacity within the OHEJP
- Contributing to future prevention, preparedness, detection and response of the EU to foodborne and other emerging threats across human-animal-environmental sectors.

Image: Pikist

Cross-Domain and Cross-Country Collaboration to Develop Multivariate Syndromic Surveillance

Name:	Skills Development Missions
Home Institute:	National Veterinary Institute (SVA), Sweden
Mission Hosting Institute:	Norwegian Institute of Public Health (NIPH), Norway
Duration of mission:	2 weeks

The aim of the STM was a collaboration and knowledge exchange between Norway and Sweden in the development of One Health systems for multivariate syndromic surveillance (SyS) of veterinary and public health data combined.

Two separate systems are in development in Sweden and Norway by the SVA and the NIPH, respectively. The Swedish system is explanatory, aiming to combine several data sources to explain outbreaks and improve the accuracy of detection. Norway, on the other hand, is developing a predictive system, which aims to use some source(s) of data to predict the outcome of others.

As a test case, both systems were evaluated on the surveillance and outbreak detection of *Campylobacter* in humans, using data from public health, broiler chicken and weather.

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...I am very grateful to the OHEJP for this opportunity. It gave me the chance to form new connections, exchange thoughts and ideas with new people. Colleagues were very welcoming: I look forward to working with them in the future. It was a rewarding experience to visit a public health institute at the doorstep of a global pandemic...”

Wiktor Gustafsson, SVA

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